

The Predictive Power of Organization Commitment and Sense of Coherence on Employees' Innovative Behavior in Academia

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Abstract

Organizations rely on fresh ideas to survive and succeed in this contemporary and cutthroat environment. The need for managers of today to seek out innovative methods has never been greater, and this research is spotlighting that need in another way. Therefore, this study determines the influence of sense of coherence and employee commitment on the employees' innovative behaviour in academia. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design and used a multi-stage sampling technique to select the 486 academic staff. Three validated questionnaires were used for data collection, which was pilot tested through test-re-test. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested. Analysis of data was done using multiple regression analysis fixed at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that with all the predictor variables (sense of coherence and organizational commitment) in the regression model jointly influenced employees' innovative behaviour ($R = .588$; $R^2 = .346$; Adj. $R^2 = .341$; $F_{(2,484)} = 10.560$; $p = .011$). The most potent predictor of employees' innovative behaviour among the predictor variables of the study is organizational commitment ($\beta = .461$; $t = 8.751$; $p < .000$) followed by sense of coherence ($\beta = .410$; $t = 5.803$; $p < .000$). The study concluded that sense of coherence and organizational commitment may serve as crucial catalysts for positive changes in the service delivery system, enhancing effectiveness, responding to demands of both work and home life, and ultimately impacting their efficiency and productivity

Keywords: *Academia, Innovative Behaviour, Lecturers, Organizational Commitment, Sense of Coherence*

INTRODUCTION

Innovation helps organizations to take advantage of fresh chances and technological advancements to continuously alter the needs and demands of their workforce, customers, and environment (Baregheh et al. 2009). Innovation potential and employee willingness are the life and death of an organization's ability to innovate (Seeck & Diehl, 2017). Employee innovation behavior predicts an organization's innovation (Prieto & Pilar Pérez-Santana, 2014). Given this knowledge, a lot of organizations place a high value on their workers' active involvement in the organizational innovation process (Cangialosi et al., 2020). Managers and executives increasingly demand that staff members go above and beyond the call of duty to advance corporate innovation goals (Maden, 2015). Due to this, many firms are interested in learning more about how to best utilize the inventive potential of their staff (Bos-Nehles et al., 2017).

The efficiency, effectiveness, and competitive advantage of both commercial and public sector innovation have been demonstrated by innovation researchers to depend critically on employee innovation behavior when it is effectively fostered (Eun, 2020; Sullivan et al., 2021). As a result, there are solid grounds to believe that encouraging employee innovation is crucial (Eun, 2020; Vivona et al., 2021).

Ideas or original ideas provide the foundation of innovation. Such ideas are frequently referred to as creative (Tan et al., 2019). According to Amabile (1988), creativity is the production or genesis of innovative ideas that are valuable and creative in the workplace. This indicates, however, that creativity alone will not result in effective innovation unless they are developed and applied (employee innovative behavior) (Carnevale et al., 2017). Understanding staff innovation behavior is crucial because measurements of innovation like productivity, profit, or the number of patents are not always available or applicable to organization's innovation (Bos-Nehles et al., 2017, Eun, 2020, Rafique et al., 2021).

Employee innovative behavior also serves as the micro-foundation for organizational innovation, as this is where new ideas are found, embraced, and put into practice by staff members. These individuals frequently go above and beyond the call of duty to find innovative ways to deliver high-quality services, suggesting new products and services, utilizing novel approaches, and securing novel funding sources (Garg & Dhar, 2017). Given that innovation rests with individuals, employee inventive behavior is therefore viewed as a valuable asset and a factor in the success of innovation in these dynamic work contexts (Riaz et al., 2018). In order to successfully embrace and improve the implementation of fresh ideas at work, employee behavior is crucial (Li & Hsu, 2016).

However, it should be mentioned that employee innovation behavior is driven by a combination of internal psychological characteristics, such as individual creative self-efficacy (Oppi et al., 2019), and external environmental factors, such as organizational social support (Suseno et al., 2019). As a result, successful innovation, effectiveness, and performance are increasingly being driven by employee creativity (Rnning, 2021). Therefore, identifying the fostering elements is still a legitimate research goal for the present study by exploring the predictive power of organization commitment and sense of coherence on employees' innovative behavior in academia.

Commitment to one's organization and a career is viewed as a person's acceptance of the value of their chosen profession or line of work as well as their belief in. This idea assumes that an employee's commitment can be shown in two ways: towards their career (career commitment) or towards their employer (organizational commitment). As a result, commitment is a complex idea. Commitment has significant effect for performance and involvement in the workplace (Adenuga et al., 2013).

According to Yukongdi and Shrestha (2020), organizational commitment is characterized as a psychological connection between an individual and an organization. Employee engagement to the innovation capabilities has also been linked to their commitment to work and their employers (Acosta et al. 2016; Moussa & Arbi, 2020). Three categories of commitments—normative commitment, affective commitment, and continuation commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Affective commitment refers to an employee's emotional bond with their affiliation and participation in the organization (Yiing & Ahmad, 2009). According to Moussa and Arbi (2020), normative commitment is the obligation to keep up one's efforts and maintain loyalty to one's employer; while continuity commitment is the commitment of the

employee in light of the expenses the individual acknowledged, including their decision to leave the company (Yiing and Ahmad, 2009).

Affective commitment is the most reliable indicator of organizational commitment (Alniaçik et al, 2013). Numerous studies have shown that the role of commitment can enhance individual motivation and performance (Nadeem, 2010; Yesil & Sozbilir, 2013; Moussa & Arbi, 2020). An employee's capacity for innovation and creativity cannot be revealed until they are dedicated to their work. They must establish their dedication during this term in order to carry out their innovative ideas (Oldham & Da Silva, 2013). Sungu et al.'s study (2019) sought to understand the causes of the mechanisms governing how organizational commitment impacts work performance. According to the research, there is a link between affective organizational commitment and job performance; also, normative organizational commitment has a favorable impact on job performance.

Sense of coherence (SOC) is the extent to which an individual has a pervasive, enduring though dynamic feeling of confidence that one's internal and external environments are predictable (Antonovsky, 1987). It is the ability to have strong belief that there is a high probability that things will work out as well in one's life. Eberez, Becker and Antoni (2015) interpreted work sense of coherence as an individual meta-resource that moderates the work-health relationship by reducing the pathogenic effects of work stressors. A strong sense of coherence is an incentive to activity.

In the course of the activity, resources, cognition schemes and competences are used more effectively, and the detrimental effect of stressors can be reduced or reversed. A concept that has been used in connection with dealing with stressful events is resilience (Mansfield, Beltman, Price & McConney, 2012; Gupta, Sood, & Bakhshi, 2012). A drop in total innovation and customer service quality may occur when a company loses its key personnel, among other things. It is undeniable that sense of coherence and employee commitment are important determinants of how workers behave in relation to achieving the organizational goal. Therefore, the present research tends to determine the influence of sense of coherence and employee commitment on the employees' innovative behaviour in academia.

Hypotheses

In order to achieve the earlier stated objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated:

1. There is no significant combined influence of employee commitment and sense of coherence on the employees' innovative behaviour.
2. There is no significant relative influence of employee commitment and sense of coherence on the employees' innovative behaviour.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: This work adopted a cross sectional survey. This design is chosen because the researcher is not going to manipulate any of the variables of the study, rather the researcher observed and described the extent of the contributions of already existing independent variables (employee commitment and sense of coherence) to the dependent variables (employees' innovative behaviour).

Population: The study population cuts across all university lecturers except non-academic staff in Ogun State. The characteristic of the study population was mixed at every university irrespective of school type (private and public) gender (male and female), age, socio-economic background, ethnicity, and cadre.

Sample size and sampling Technique: In Ogun State, there are ten (10) accredited universities. Three (3) are owned by the government, and seven (7) are owned by private or religious organizations. In order to conduct this study, a sample of 486 academic staff members was chosen. The different faculties/schools were chosen using a multi-stage sampling technique. Due to its stage-by-stage sample mechanism, the multi-stage sampling method was chosen. First, the institutions were chosen using a stratified random sample technique, which divided them into private and public (federal and state) ownership categories. Second, using the balloting method of random sampling, four (4) colleges—two (2) private and two (2) public—were chosen from the category of either private or public universities. Thirdly, the faculties or schools within the chosen universities were once more divided into two categories: (1) those that are science-oriented and (2) those that are not. One faculty or school from each category was then chosen based on the stratification, giving the universities a total of two faculties. This demonstrates that a total of eight (8) faculties or schools took part in the investigation. Again, a simple random sampling was performed to select one faculty department from each faculty. Lastly, 486 lecturers were chosen using the proportionate stratified random sampling approach.

Instrumentation: In order to respond to the questionnaire, participants were required to check a box next to one of the possible replies. A Likert scale of 1 to 5 is used to rate each response for agreement or disagreement with the statement under consideration. Twelve statement items adapted from De Jong and Hartog (2010) are used to measure innovative behavior. A total of fifteen statement items from Ellinger et al. (2013) that were constructed are used to assess commitment. Thirteen item statements based on Antonovsky's (1987) work are used to assess sense of coherence.

Method of Data Analysis: The information gathered by the scales and questionnaires was examined using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). To examine part A, which touches on demographic data, frequency counts and percentages were used. All of the hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis to determine the combined impact of independent and dependent variables. For testing all of the hypotheses, the significance threshold was set at 0.05.

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary of the regression analysis for the combined influence of organizational commitment and sense of coherence on the prediction of employees' innovative behaviour

Model	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	SE	Change Statistics				
					R ² Change	F Change	d f 1	d f 2	Sig. F Change
Predictor Variables	.588	.346	.341	13.216	.341	10.560	2	484	.011

- a. Predictions: (Constant), commitment, sense of coherence
- b. Dependent Variable: innovative work behaviour

The results in Table 1 indicated that with all the predictor variables (sense of coherence and organizational commitment) in the regression model jointly influenced employees' innovative behaviour ($R = .588$; $R^2 = .346$; $\text{Adj. } R^2 = .341$; $F_{(2,484)} = 10.560$; $p = .011$). This showed that all the predictor variables accounted for 34.1% of the variance to employees' innovative behaviour. The null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence of organizational commitment and sense of coherence on employees' innovative behaviour was rejected by this finding. This implies that there is a significant combined influence of organizational commitment and sense of coherence on employees' innovative behaviour.

Table 2: Beta Coefficients for relative contributions of organizational commitment and sense of coherence on the prediction of employees' innovative behaviour

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-ratio	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)		
(Constant)	34.206	10.119		9.610	.000
Sense of coherence	.254	.121	.410	5.803	.000
Commitment	.323	.160	.461	8.751	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employees' work behaviour

The results in Table 4.2.2 revealed the strength of causation of the predictor variable on the criterion variable. It was shown that all the two (2) predictors were potent enough to predict employees' innovative behaviour. The most potent predictor of employees' innovative behaviour among the predictor variables of the study is organizational commitment ($\beta = .461$; $t = 8.751$; $p < .000$). Sense of coherence is the next potent factor ($\beta = .410$; $t = 5.803$; $p < .000$) in the prediction of employees' innovative behaviour.

The hypothesis of no significant relative influence of organizational commitment and sense of coherence on employees' innovative behaviour was rejected by this finding. This implies that there is a significant relative contribution of organizational commitment and sense of coherence on employees' innovative behaviour, while organizational commitment was observed as the most potent predictor between the two.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The first hypothesis stated that there is no significant influence of organizational commitment and sense of coherence on employees' innovative behaviour. This hypothesis was rejected by the analysis of data indicating that organizational commitment and sense of coherence contributed to the prediction of employees' innovative behaviour. Result showed that organizational commitment and sense of coherence accounted for the variance observed in the employees' innovative behaviour. The implication of this result is that for employees' innovative behaviour to be well tapped into, organizational commitment and sense of coherence cannot be overruled.

Previous research (Amankwaa et al., 2019; Hakim ian et al., 2016; Marques et al., 2014; Nguyen et al., 2019) corroborated these findings that organizational commitment strengthened in innovative work behaviour. Additionally, studies have shown that the role of commitment can enhance individual motivation and performance (Yesil & Sozbilir, 2013; Moussa & Arbi, 2020). An employee's capacity for innovation and creativity cannot be revealed until they are dedicated to their work. They must establish their dedication in order to carry out their innovative ideas (Oldham & Da Silva, 2013). Therefore, the level of commitment people have

with the company they work for suggests the employee intent to work hard for the company and is willing to commit a significant amount of time to frequently go above and beyond the call of duty to find innovative ways to deliver high-quality services, suggesting new products and services, utilizing novel approaches, and securing novel funding sources

The results also demonstrate that sense of coherence is an excellent predictor of workers' inventive behavior, which shields them from burnout. When an individual has a strong sense of coherence, they are able to gather the necessary resources for a particular professional situation and utilize them effectively.

Recognizing work-related emotions also helps in dealing with issues more effectively, and when problems seem insurmountable, it aids in adapting. In response to stress, sense of coherence acts as a buffer, according to the findings of numerous studies (Eberez, Becker, & Antoni, 2015). With the help of this buffer, one may accept life's unavoidable challenges (Eberez, Becker, & Antoni, 2015), experience more life satisfaction (Ayodele & Adebunsi, 2018), and have improved self-control due to reduced anxiety and hostility (Ezeokoli & Ayodele, 2014).

One plausible reason for the findings of this study may be adduced to the fact that individual innovative behaviour entails the actions in which individuals engage that influence their work productivity positively or negatively. This study suggests that favourable changes in individual innovative behaviour were significantly associated with positive changes in additional value added through commitment and sense of coherence.

CONCLUSION

Overall, the study's findings provided important new insights into how organizational commitment and feeling of coherence may serve as a buffer for workers' innovative behavior. The benefit of this study's findings is that they may serve as crucial catalysts for positive changes in the service delivery system, enhancing effectiveness, responding to demands of both work and home life, and ultimately impacting their efficiency and productivity. In reality, the educational system will be able to concentrate more on the lecturers' productivity and finding useful tactics to improve it.

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